

VBEAM LASER TREATMENT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10242668>

Abstract: *This article provides complete information about the Vbeam laser treatment. The Vbeam® Laser pulsed dye laser is a versatile device that was designed primarily for the treatment of cosmetic vascular issues, and can also be used for treating pigmented lesions. In addition, the Vbeam system uses targeted laser therapy to treat redness, acne, wrinkles, and sunspots on the face and chest.*

Keywords: *Vbeam, laser, redness, acne, wrinkles, scar, pigmentation, oxyhemoglobin, melanin, treatment.*

The Vbeam® laser system is a world-renowned, easy-to-use pulsed dye laser recognized as the gold standard technology for the treatment of vascular lesions. The Vbeam pulsed dye laser (PDL) has been proven time and again for the successful treatment of a wide array of vascular, pigmented, and certain non-pigmented lesions, with a low incidence of side effects.

The system uses 595 nm PDL technology to deliver an intense but gentle burst of light into targeted areas of the skin. There it's absorbed by the blood vessels or melanin pigmented areas, removing the targeted imperfections. Most patients notice results right away, and it's clinically proven for multiple skin types.

Vbeam pulsed dye laser (PDL) at a wavelength of 595nm or 1064nm passes through the epidermal and dermal layers of the skin and is absorbed by the oxyhemoglobin in the blood vessels rather than by the surrounding tissue.

Some of the specific problems that can be treated with this device include:

- Broken blood vessels;
- Rosacea;
- Spider veins;
- Vascular lesions;
- Scars;
- Hyperpigmentation.

Vbeam®

Laser treatments for birthmarks, port wine stains, redness, rosacea, dark spots, facial and leg veins, wrinkles, and acne. The Vbeam system is FDA and CE cleared. The Vbeam family includes: Vbeam Perfecta®, and Vbeam Prima®.

Vbeam Laser Treatment Highlights

In a clinical study, a Vbeam 595 nm pulsed dye laser was used to treat infants with port wine stains, resulting in an average port wine stain clearance of 88.6% after a year of treatment.

Rosacea / Redness Treatments

In a clinical study, after an average of 2.6 Vbeam 595 nm laser treatments, patients with blood vessels on the face had a visual improvement of 75% to 100%.

Acne Treatments

In a clinical study, Vbeam 595 nm laser therapy cleared more than 90% of inflammatory acne lesions in treated patients.

Scar and Stretch Mark Treatments

In a clinical study, all scars treated with a Vbeam 595 nm pulsed dye laser showed a significant improvement in appearance.

TREATMENT RESULTS

Vbeam laser treatments are customized to meet your individual skincare needs. The number and duration of treatments will depend on the condition and your skin type. You can typically expect 2 to 4 treatment sessions, each lasting 15 to 30 minutes.

Patients treated with a Vbeam laser system reported experiencing minimal discomfort during treatment. In fact, they were highly satisfied with the results:

- ✓ 100% of patients treated for facial wrinkles reported being satisfied with their results.
- ✓ After 3 treatments, patients had over a 90% reduction in small red veins and dark brown spots.

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